

Wheely Easy: Creating a Wheelability Network for Bradford

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Summary

This study develops a methodological framework for constructing a wheelability network that captures wheelchair-specific mobility constraints. Using mobile LiDAR data and an initial classification model, we extract road geometry and apply a skeletonisation-based geometric workflow to detect dropped kerbs. Sidewalks are extracted and reduced to centrelines, from which slope and width metrics are used to compute a Wheelability index. Integrating these indices with dropped-kerb connectivity yields a comprehensive network representing real wheelchair navigability. By highlighting dropped kerbs as essential mobility elements, this work advances wheelability assessment beyond existing pedestrian-focused approaches.

KEYWORDS: Wheelability, LiDAR, Dropped Kerbs, Inclusive Street Design

1. Introduction

Walkability is widely studied in urban research, yet much literature rests on an implicit assumption of an able-bodied pedestrian, thereby overlooking wheelchair-specific mobility needs (Shields *et al.*, 2023). The limited consideration of *wheelability* reflects both a conceptual focus on pedestrian experience and constraints imposed by available data. Most assessments rely on image-based assessments such as street-view imagery, which do not support detailed geometric analysis of sidewalks and remain confined to pedestrian-oriented indicators. Consequently, wheelchair accessibility is often limited through non-automated or field-based audit tools (Deturbide & Terashima, 2025).

Recent advances in mobile LiDAR and deep learning have lowered the technical barrier to extracting sidewalk infrastructure at scale, enabling network-level modelling of pedestrian surfaces with detailed geometric attributes (Hou & Ai, 2020). Building on this capability, a growing body of research has incorporated sidewalk width and slope into quantitative assessments of wheelability, using 3D point clouds to quantify wheelchair mobility constraints. (Meng *et al.*, 2025; Ning, 2025). However, wheelchair mobility is particularly sensitive to the presence and quality of dropped kerbs, which enable transitions between sidewalks and roadways and are explicitly recognised as essential accessibility elements in inclusive street design guidelines (Department for Transport, 2021).

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This study proposes a methodology to detect dropped kerbs from high-resolution mobile LiDAR data integrated with sidewalk slope and width metrics to construct a comprehensive wheelability network, demonstrated using real-world data from neighbourhoods within Bradford. By anchoring accessibility assessment in 3D geometry, the approach advances street-level modelling of wheelchair-specific accessibility (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1 Conceptual overview of the proposed wheelability network approach.

2. Data

The project utilises high-resolution mobile mapping point-cloud data collected using a Leica TRK700 Evo Mobile Mapping System, which generates up to 4 million points per second. The system offers potential for a continuous view of the street network at an unprecedented level of detail. The equipment is vehicle-mounted and where necessary is driven along survey routes twice, to minimise occlusions and improve geometric accuracy. Raw point-cloud data are automatically colourised using imagery from the onboard panoramic camera for later classification tasks.

Our analysis focuses on areas within Bradford, offering a range of commercial and pedestrian routeways undergoing regeneration. The area contains diverse street typologies, varied kerb structures, and complex elevation changes—conditions suitable for testing automated dropped kerb extraction and wheelability network construction.

3. Method

3.1. Point Cloud Pre-classification

The raw point clouds are first processed in Leica Cyclone 3DR using its pre-trained road-classification model. This automated step identifies two primary data classes: road surface and kerbs, forming the initial layers for downstream analysis. However, because the model is trained predominantly on U.S. road data, kerb predictions are not sufficiently accurate for UK street geometries, particularly at older high-street kerb lines. Consequently, the two extracted classes are merged and treated collectively as road data for all downstream processing.

3.2. Automated Identification of Dropped Kerbs

To stabilise height variation and reduce noise, the merged road data are meshed into a 3D model (**Figure 2**). The meshed road is mapped onto a regular 10 cm XY grid as a computational framework

for local neighbourhood analysis

Figure 2 Meshed 3D model of the road point cloud.

For each grid cell, we compute the vertical Z-range. Cells exceeding 5cm in height variation are marked as kerb candidates, reflecting the threshold at which wheelchair users typically face a barrier (**Figure 3**). This grid-based geometric method provides improved interpretability and greater accuracy than relying on the kerb class predicted by the Cyclone 3DR model.

Figure 3 Binary map of grid height ranges > 5cm (potential kerbs)

To capture the structure of the kerb, kerb-candidate cells are processed using skeletonisation, applying the classical thinning approach of Zhang and Suen (1984) to obtain one-pixel-wide medial lines. The kerb skeleton is then divided into individual segments through connected-component labelling (**Figure 4**), and geometric properties (e.g., segment length) are extracted for each component.

Figure 4 Extracted kerb candidates after skeletonisation.

For the remaining segments, we compute the nearest endpoints between every pair of segments to identify locations where two kerb lines terminate in close proximity—an expected geometric signature of a potential dropped kerb. Following wheelchair accessibility design guidance, the distance between matched endpoints is used as the final classification criterion: gaps under 1.5m were classified as noise, gaps over 5.0m as junctions, and gaps within this range were detected as dropped kerbs (**Figure 5**).

Figure 5 Detected Dropped Kerbs.

3.3. Extraction and Assessment of the Sidewalk

Sidewalks are extracted from the point cloud dataset by reconstructing a relative ground-height plane from the scanner's elevation readings. After meshing the road surface, all planar regions located more

than 5cm above this reference plane are identified as sidewalk candidates. These elevated surfaces are rasterised and processed using skeletonisation to obtain a one-pixel-wide centreline, providing a stable geometric representation for evaluating local slope and width.

Slopes are computed from elevation gradients along the centreline. Following *Inclusive Mobility* guidance (Department for Transport, 2021), slopes below 5% are generally considered accessible, whereas slopes exceeding 10% impose substantial difficulty for manual wheelchair users. To map these thresholds onto a continuous slope sub-index, we employ a smooth transition function that ensures a differentiable, non-abrupt decline in accessibility:

$$T(x; a, b) = \min(1, \max(0, 3u^2 - 2u^3)), \quad u = \frac{x - a}{b - a} \quad (1)$$

where x is the coordinate along the segment, and a and b denote the start and end locations.

The slope wheelability sub-index is then defined as:

$$W_{\text{slope}} = 1 - T(s; 2\%, 10\%) \quad (2)$$

yielding full accessibility below 2%, a progressive decline across intermediate gradients, and a value of zero for slopes greater than 10%.

Sidewalk width is measured as the shortest distance from the centreline to the sidewalk boundary. UK standards specify that widths below 1.0 m restrict independent wheelchair use, while 2.0 m allows comfortable two-way passing. The width sub-index is therefore:

$$W_{\text{width}} = T(w; 1.0, 2.0) \quad (3)$$

which increases smoothly from 0 to 1 across the admissible width range.

The final sidewalk wheelability index combines these geometric criteria multiplicatively:

$$W = W_{\text{width}} \times W_{\text{slope}} \quad (4)$$

reflecting constraints from insufficient width or excessive slope (**Figure 6**). This formulation provides a continuous, interpretable measure of sidewalk accessibility and integrates seamlessly with dropped-kerb detections within the broader Wheelability Indicator.

Figure 6 Wheelability index and width/slope of the sidewalk

3.4. Construction of the Wheelability Network

The final wheelability network is constructed by integrating the sidewalk wheelability values with the detected dropped-kerb locations into a unified pedestrian-accessibility framework. Sidewalk segments are connected through pairs of aligned dropped kerbs, forming potential crossing links that represent where wheelchair users can safely transition between footways. This produces a continuous network in which each link and node carries an accessibility score reflecting real-world wheelchair navigability.

The resulting wheelability network can support accessible pathfinding, highlight critical barriers, and provide an evidence base for targeted planning interventions for inclusive street-design (**Figure 7**).

Wheelability Networks

Figure 7 Conceptual Schematic of the wheelability network.

4. Initial Results

Initial testing of the workflow has been conducted on a 3km sample of Bradford’s mobile mapping data (**Figure 8**), showing strong agreement between dropped-kerb detection and manually inspected ground-truth observations, thus demonstrating the feasibility and accuracy of the approach.

Figure 8 Detected kerbs and dropped kerbs of sample data.

5. Ongoing Work

Current work focuses the analysis of sidewalk surfaces, including extraction, centreline generation, and evaluation of slope and width conditions. These components will enable construction of a complete wheelability network, integrating sidewalk accessibility with dropped-kerb connectivity.

The next stage extends the workflow to a larger dataset from the Bradford area, allowing continuous modelling of wheelchair navigability across a larger urban area, to support accessible pathfinding,

reveal priority locations for intervention, and provide a data-driven basis for inclusive transport planning.

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Biographies

Chenrui Xiao is a Data Scientist at the Leeds Institute for Data Analytics, working at the intersection of data science and urban spatial research. He is interested in how computational methods can reveal urban dynamics and mobility patterns, with current work focusing on LiDAR-based modelling of wheelchair mobility.

Victoria Houlden is an Associate Professor in Urban Data Science in the School of Geography, University of Leeds. She aims to understand the ways in which spaces and places embody inequalities, and the social structures influencing how people relate to their environment. Her current projects focus on greenspace access.

Jennie Gray is an ECR, working as a Research Fellow at the University of Leeds. She is interested in all facets of neighbourhood research, the sociodemographic processes cultivating changes, the spatiotemporal properties of those changes, and finally the human consequences of them, notably socio-spatial inequalities and their impacts on accessibility.

Markus Billeter is a Lecturer in Computer Graphics in the School of Computer Science, University of Leeds. He focuses on high-performance data structures and algorithms for real-time rendering with the goal to efficiently utilize hardware (e.g., GPUs). One application of this relates to large sparse 3D voxel structures.

Tom Sparrow is Senior Scientist in the Institute of Digital & Sustainable Futures at the University of Bradford, and researcher on the Healthy Urban Places project. He has more than 15 years experience as researcher within the Visualising Heritage Team and was responsible for spec'ing the mobile mapping infrastructure.

Andrew S. Wilson is a Professor in the Institute of Digital & Sustainable Futures at the University of Bradford, Co-I on the Healthy Urban Places project and is academic lead for the Visualising Heritage Team and PI on AHRC-funded mobile mapping infrastructure (via AH/V01255X/1) that generated the primary data.